

CARTAN-SIEGEL HOMOGENEOUS DOMAINS: SIEGEL DISK

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6567409>

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Siegel Disk has been introduced by Carl Ludwig Siegel through Symplectic Group $Sp_{2n}R$ that is one possible generalization of the group $SL_2R = Sp_2R$ (group of invertible matrices with determinant 1) to higher dimensions. This generalization goes further; since they act on a symmetric homogeneous space, the Siegel upper half plane, and this action has quite a few similarities with the action of SL_2R on the Poincaré's hyperbolic plane [1].

Let F be either the real or the complex field, the Symplectic Group is the group of all matrices $M \in GL_{2n}F$ satisfying:

$$Sp(n, F) = \{M \in GL(2n, F) / M^T J M = J\}, \quad J = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & I_n \\ -I_n & 0 \end{pmatrix} \in SL(2n, R) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{or } M = \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{pmatrix} \in Sp(n, F) \Leftrightarrow A^T C \text{ and } B^T D \text{ symmetric} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{and } A^T D - C^T B = I_n.$$

The Siegel upper half plane is the set of all complex symmetric $n \times n$ matrices with positive definite imaginary part (fig. 1):

$$SH_n = \{Z = X + iY \in \text{Sym}(n, C) / \text{Im}(Z) = Y > 0\} \quad (3)$$

Figure 1. Geometry of Siegel Upper Half-Plane

The action of the Symplectic Group on the Siegel upper half plane is transitive. The group $PSp(n, R) \equiv Sp(n, R) / \{\pm I_{2n}\}$ is group of SH_n biholomorphisms via generalized Möbius transformations:

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{pmatrix} \Rightarrow M(Z) = (AZ+B)(CZ+D)^{-1} \quad (4)$$

$PSp(n, R)$ acts as a sub-group of isometries. Siegel has proved that Symplectic transformations are isometries for the Siegel metric in SH_n . It can be defined on SH_n using the distance element at the point $Z=X+iY$, as defined by:

$$ds^2_{Siegel} = Tr(Y^{-1}(dZ)Y^{-1}(dZ^+)) \text{ with } Z=X+iY \quad (5)$$

with associated volume form : $\Omega=Tr(Y^{-1}dZ \wedge Y^{-1}dZ^+)$.

C.L. Siegel has proved [2] that distance in Siegel Upper-Half Plane is given by:

$$d^2_{Siegel}(Z_1, Z_2) = \left(\sum_{k=1}^n \log^2 \left(\frac{1+\sqrt{r_k}}{1-\sqrt{r_k}} \right) \right) \text{ with } Z_1, Z_2 \in SH_n \quad (6)$$

and r_k eigenvalues of the cross-ratio:

$$R(Z_1, Z_2) = (Z_1 - Z_2)(Z_1 - Z_2^+)^{-1}(Z_1 - Z_2^+)(Z_1^+ - Z_2)^{-1}. \quad (7)$$

This is deduced from the 2nd derivative of $Z \rightarrow R(Z_1, Z)$ in $Z_1=Z$ given by:

$$D^2R = 2dZ(Z-Z^+)^{-1}dZ^+(Z^+-Z)^{-1} = (1/2)dZY^{-1}dZ^+Y^{-1} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{and } ds^2 = Tr(Y^{-1}dZY^{-1}dZ^+) = 2Tr(D^2R) \quad (9)$$

In parallel, in China in 1945, Hua Lookeng[3] has given the equations of geodesic in Siegel upper-half plane:

$$\frac{d^2Z}{ds^2} + i \frac{dZ}{ds} Y^{-1} \frac{dZ}{ds} = 0 \quad (10)$$

Using generalized Cayley transform $W=(Z-iI_n)(Z+iI_n)^{-1}$ Siegel Upper-half Plane SH_n is transformed in unit Siegel disk $SD_n=W/WW^+ < I_n$ where the metric in Siegel Disk is given by (see [4-7]):

$$ds^2 = Tr[(I_n - WW^+)^{-1}dW(I_n - W^+W)^{-1}dW^+] \quad (11)$$

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